

SUPPLEMENTAL MATERIAL

Supplemental Fig. 1. Effect of tenapanor, sevelamer, and the combination of tenapanor and sevelamer on body weight in rats. Data are shown as mean \pm standard error of the mean.

Supplemental Fig. 2. Effect of tenapanor, sevelamer, and the combination of tenapanor and sevelamer on 24-hour food intake in rats. Data are shown as mean \pm standard error of the mean.

Supplemental Fig. 3. The calculated dose of sevelamer delivered by diet admixture in rats treated with and without tenapanor. Data are shown as mean±standard error of the mean.